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Glass Tumbling for Safe Waste Glass Disposal in Cape Maclear, Malawi

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ABSTRACT

Glass waste is an increasing environmental challenge, particularly in communities with limited waste management infrastructure. In Cape Maclear, Malawi, rapid growth in tourism has caused a sharp rise in imported glass bottles, which are often discarded without treatment. Broken glass persists in the environment for long periods, creating ongoing safety hazards for residents, waste workers, and visitors. Conventional approaches, such as bottle crushing, have proven difficult to operate on a larger scale and often produce fragments that remain hazardous to handle. This research therefore aimed to investigate whether tumbling, a process commonly employed in industrial finishing and mineral processing, could offer a simple, low-tech solution for rendering glass waste safe.

A prototype tumbling machine was designed, constructed, and tested, emphasizing simplicity, affordability, and the use of widely available or repurposed materials. The machine comprises rotating drums made from repurposed gas cylinders, supported by parallel shafts and driven by a salvaged electric motor. The prototype was tested with waste glass collected from discarded bottles, broken into fragments, and subjected to multiple tumbling cycles. During testing, glass fragment sharpness was assessed through tactile and visual inspection, while fragment size distribution and machine performance, including energy consumption, were also monitored.

Results indicated that tumbling effectively dulls sharp glass edges, with most transformation occurring within the first hour of operation. Larger fragments dulled more quickly, whereas fragments smaller than ten millimeters required several hours of tumbling to reach comparable safety levels. Operating speed was identified as a critical parameter: moderate speeds minimized the occurrence of new fractures and the formation of fresh sharp edges. Contrary to expectations, tumbling did not consistently reduce the size of large fragments, indicating that complementary methods would be necessary if size reduction is also a goal. Finally, the machine design proved robust, although improvements were noted primarily in vibration control and in the selection of structural and mechanical construction materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

This thesis covers the conception, construction and testing of a new method in order to turn waste glass into a safe material, in the context of its implementation in Cape Maclear, a town in the Mangochi district in Malawi.

1.1 Cape Maclear: Geographical and Socioeconomic Background

Cape Maclear, also known as Chembe, is a remote village located on the southern tip of the Lake Malawi, in the Mangochi District of Malawi. The village has undergone a significant transformation from its origins as a small fishing village of approximately 2,000 people in the late 1990s, to becoming one of Malawi's most popular tourist destinations, with a population that has exploded to nearly 20,000 individuals (Mahdjoub *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 1.1. Geographical location of Malawi and Cape Maclear

Although tourism provides a source of income, Cape Maclear remains an isolated community in rural Malawi—a country persistently ranked among the world’s poorest and most corrupt, and whose economy depends heavily on agriculture (Mtuwa, 2023; Stricker, 2024). As a result, residents continue to struggle with basic needs, including the collection and treatment of municipal solid waste. This challenge is intensified by tourist-driven demand for comfort and consumer goods, which significantly increases the volume of waste beyond what the village previously experienced (Mahdjoub N., 2021).

In addition to the increased waste generated by tourism, the village also suffers from its own waste due to the absence of a formal municipal waste collection service. Without organized waste management, numerous informal dumpsites have emerged, with waste accumulating in piles and household refuse frequently burned in the open. This challenge is further compounded by the very low electrification rate in the Mangochi district (2–5%), which causes frequent power outages and limits the use of waste treatment machinery that relies on the national electricity grid (Sustainable Energy for All, 2022). This unmanaged situation not only endangers the health and environment of the local population but also undermines Cape Maclear’s image as a leading tourist destination.

1.2 Waste Glass in Cape Maclear

Waste glass is a growing environmental concern worldwide, particularly in regions lacking adequate recycling infrastructure. Unlike organic matter, glass does not decompose, resulting in its persistent accumulation in landfills and the environment (Ferdous *et al.*, 2021). Once broken, glass becomes hazardous, increasing the risk of physical injuries, especially when improperly disposed of (Ali & Yusuf, 2021; Al-Khatib, 2009). This issue is especially pressing in Cape Maclear, where the recent surge in tourism has significantly increased the amount of waste glass scattered throughout the village (Colbach, 2024). Indeed, tourists are the main consumer for imported bottled goods that do not have a deposit like the rest of the bottles in Malawi making the imported bottles a major source of this waste glass.

In the absence of a structured recycling or disposal system, discarded glass often ends up in informal dumpsites or dispersed across the village, leading to both environmental degradation and public health hazards, such as injuries from broken shards and persistent pollution (Colbach, 2024; Meier, 2024; Tilley & Tkaczuk, 2024).

To address this pressing issue, the Global Health Engineering (GHE) Laboratory has conducted several projects in collaboration with a local NGO (Sustainable Cape Maclear), aiming to explore potential methods for glass valorization (Mahdjoub *et al.*, 2020; Mahdjoub N., 2021) and to investigate transformation methods to facilitate its management and recycling (Colbach,

2024).

This master's thesis builds upon these previous efforts and contributes an additional element toward a broader response to the challenge of waste glass accumulation in Cape Maclear.

1.3 Justification and Research Questions

Glass waste poses a persistent environmental and safety challenge, particularly in communities with limited waste management infrastructure. The primary objective of this project is to explore methods to transform sharp shards from broken bottles into smooth and dull pieces, effectively converting waste glass into a safe material. Ensuring that glass is rendered safe allows for its long-term secure storage, reducing the risk of injury even if the storage location changes. In this study, a glass piece is considered safe when it has no sharp edges remaining.

The choice of tumbling as a processing method arises from the limitations observed in a prior attempt to construct a glass bottle crusher in late 2023 (Colbach, 2024). While the crusher prototype demonstrated potential, its operational complexity, safety hazards, and the dangerous nature of the resulting fragments limited its practical effectiveness. These challenges underscored the need for alternative approaches to make waste glass safe for both the inhabitants of the village and waste management personnel.

Tumbling is a well-established technique in metal manufacturing and aggregate processing for smoothing sharp edges and eliminating burrs (DeGarmo P, 2003). Typical tumbling machines consist of a rotating cylinder containing the material to be processed. As the cylinder rotates, the material is lifted by centrifugal forces and falls back onto itself, producing friction and impact that progressively dulls edges. One key advantage of tumbling is that the material itself serves as the grinding media, which minimizes wear on machine components and tooling, reducing maintenance requirements and initial equipment costs.

Building on the uses of tumbling in industrial applications, this master's thesis investigates whether the process is suitable for treating waste glass to achieve safe handling and long-term storage. The research is organized around the following questions:

1. Is tumbling an adequate solution for processing waste glass safely in the context of Cape Maclear, ensuring its secure and long-term disposal?
2. How much tumbling time is required to reduce the sharpness of glass to a safe level?
3. How does the size distribution of glass fragments evolve during the tumbling process?

The expected outcome of this thesis is to provide data and insights demonstrating that tumbling is a viable method for processing waste glass, enabling its safe, sustainable, and long-term storage in communities similar to Cape Maclear.

2 METHODS

The project was conducted in four distinct phases:

1. Theoretical design of a tumbling machine.
2. Construction of a prototype.
3. Experimental tests on waste glass tumbling.
4. Data processing and analysis.

Among these, the theoretical design and process testing represented the majority of the workload.

2.1 Design & Construction of a Tumbler Machine

2.1.1 Requirements and General Architecture

Main Requirement The machine must process the total daily waste glass produced in Cape Maclear within 24 hours, ensuring that the glass becomes sufficiently dull for safe handling.

Secondary Requirements The following additional criteria were defined (in no particular order):

- **Expandable design:** Architecture should allow for future capacity increases to accommodate higher waste volumes.
- **Independent drum operation:** Drums are not rigidly fixed, allowing multiple tumbling cycles at different stages of completion to be run simultaneously and removed at different times.
- **Ergonomics:** Loading and unloading must be simple and avoid lifting heavy loads above waist height.

- **Weather resistance:** The machine must be operable and storable outdoors.
- **Reliability:** The machine should require minimal intervention between cycles and allow for straightforward maintenance and repair.
- **Low-tech approach:** Construction should rely on widely available, inexpensive tools and require minimal technical expertise to build and operate.

To meet these requirements, the proposed machine architecture comprises rotating drums containing the waste glass, supported by two parallel shafts. An electric motor drives one shaft through a belt-and-pulley transmission, with drum rotation achieved via friction between the drums and the shafts.

2.1.2 Mechanical Design of the Machine and Drums

The initial stage of the mechanical design focused on selecting the drum type and dimensions to ensure adequate capacity for the daily volume of waste glass. According to (Meier, 2024), approximately 48.8 kg of waste glass is generated each day by the inhabitants and lodges of Cape Maclear. Given their global availability, robust construction, and thick steel walls, repurposed 13 kg butane/propane cylinders were selected as the drum base. When filled to two-thirds of their volume, each modified cylinder provides an estimated capacity of 25.66 kg, assuming a bulk density of 1340 kg/m³ (Deco Stones, 2019). Using two drums in parallel results in a total capacity of 51.32 kg, slightly exceeding the estimated daily waste glass production of Cape Maclear.

The subsequent design step was to determine the minimum shaft diameter capable of supporting the drums when fully loaded with waste glass. The total load on the shaft corresponds to the combined mass of the drum ($m_{\text{drum}} = 11$ kg) and the contained waste glass ($m_{\text{glass}} = 25.7$ kg). A safety factor of $SF = 3$ was applied to account for operational uncertainties (shocks and vibrations mostly). The load was modeled as a point force at the midpoint between two bearings separated by the drum length plus the bearing offsets ($L = 0.45 + 2 \times 0.075 = 0.60$ m).

The maximum force and bending moment were computed as:

$$F = (m_{\text{drum}} + m_{\text{glass}}) \cdot g \cdot SF$$

$$M = \frac{F \cdot L}{4}$$

where $g = 9.81$ m/s² is gravitational acceleration.

Assuming a solid circular shaft and using the elastic limit σ of the chosen material (here 304L stainless steel, $\sigma_{304L} = 170$ MPa), the minimum required diameter was obtained from the bending strength equation:

$$d_{304L} = \left(\frac{32M}{\pi \sigma_{304L}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

The resulting value, expressed in millimeters, ensures that the shaft operates below the elastic limit of the material under the specified loading conditions. Below, in Table 2.1, are the obtained values for several materials: 304L and 316L stainless steel, S235 structural steel, and 6060 aluminium. These materials were selected due to their local availability.

Table 2.1. Minimum shaft diameter for different materials under specified loading conditions

Material	d_{circ} [mm]
304L Stainless Steel	21.33
316L Stainless Steel	20.21
6060 Aluminium Alloy	27.43
S235 Structural Steel	19.15

The MATLAB code used for these calculations, along with additional results for annular shaft profiles, is provided in the Appendix A. Based on the results, two shafts with a diameter of 25 mm were selected for design and purchased in 304L stainless steel, chosen for its availability and superior resistance to water-related corrosion.

The structure was designed as a simple wooden frame with a height of 42 cm, allowing loading and unloading without lifting the drums above waist level. Wood was selected for its wide availability, ease of workability, low cost, and high toughness (Imakawa K., 2022). Assembly was carried out using wood screws, metal plates, and brackets to enhance rigidity. A simplified CAD design of the structure can be seen at the Figure 2.1.

To ensure the machine could withstand prolonged outdoor storage and operation, several weatherproofing measures were implemented: exclusively stainless steel was used for metallic assembly components; sealed bearings with aluminum casings were selected; the wooden structure was coated with two layers of marine-grade varnish; and a protective cover for the motor and electronics was constructed from repurposed office storage boxes.

The drums were fabricated from 13L gas bottles, modified to include a side opening that can be closed with a movable metal plate secured by six M8 bolts. This configuration ensures adequate compression of the opening during testing, to limit the release of glass dust, and allowing the addition of a rubber seal if proved to be necessary. To improve structural rigidity, the horizontal plates were reinforced with six ribs, as shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1. Simplified CAD design of the machine's structure

Figure 2.2. CAD design of the drum, without closing plate

2.1.3 Powertrain Design

The powertrain of the tumbling machine is composed of three main components: the power transmission system, the electric motor, and the motor speed controller. These elements were selected with the goal of ensuring simplicity, durability, and accessibility of replacement parts, particularly in locations with limited resources such as Cape Maclear.

Power Transmission: The chosen power transmission system uses a set of pulleys and a belt. Compared to chain-and-sprocket systems or gear assemblies, this solution offers several advantages: it requires no lubrication, operates quietly, demands little maintenance, and tolerates less precise alignment during assembly. These characteristics make it a reliable and user-friendly choice for low-maintenance operation.

Electric Motor Selection: To keep the design low-tech and ensure easy sourcing of parts, the motor type needed to be widely available worldwide. Universal motors were selected for this purpose, as they are commonly found in consumer appliances such as blenders, hand-held drills, and washing machines. These motors are brushed, series-wound machines with an armature and field windings mounted on a laminated core. Brushes rest against the commutator to supply current and reverse its direction as the armature rotates within the magnetic field. Their drawbacks include relatively low efficiency and brush wear over time, but their wide availability, ease of control, and low cost—especially when salvaged from discarded appliances—outweigh these limitations.

An additional advantage of universal motors is their compatibility with both mains AC voltage and DC sources such as solar panels. This allows the machine to operate from grid power or renewable energy, depending on availability. The choice of power source determines the appropriate motor controller.

Motor Speed Control:

- **With mains AC supply:** The voltage must be reduced to control speed effectively. A

TRIAC-based controller is a simple and inexpensive option for this purpose : It adjusts the conduction angle of the AC waveform, reducing the effective voltage supplied to the motor and allowing precise speed regulation. The electrical schematic can be seen below in the schematic in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3. Electrical schematic of an universal motor and TRIAC setup, connected to mains electricity

- **With DC supply (e.g., solar panels):** Universal motors perform better at higher voltages, as this increases torque, speed, and efficiency. Since solar panels typically output 12 or 24 V DC, the voltage must first be increased using a DC-DC converter. As solar panel power output is unstable, a solar charge controller is recommended to stabilize the voltage supply before conversion. Adding a battery after the charge controller would further allow continuous operation of the machine during periods of reduced solar power generation. For optimal motor control, the armature and field windings can be electrically isolated and powered by separate DC-DC converters-one controlling torque (field windings) and the other controlling rotational speed (armature). DC-DC converters are widely used in electronics and industry, making them readily available in most regions, including countries of the Global South such as Malawi. The electrical schematic can be seen below in the schematic in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4. Electrical schematic of an universal motor and solar panel setup

Optimal rotation speed calculation: The tumbling process is most efficient when the drum rotates just below the critical speed, i.e., the speed at which particles are pressed against the wall by centrifugal force and no relative motion occurs between them. The critical speed can be estimated solely from the drum geometry using the following formula (Wills B., 2006):

$$N_c = \frac{42.3}{\sqrt{D_{\text{int}}}}$$

where N_c is the critical speed in rpm and D_{int} is the internal diameter of the drum (in meters).

For optimal tumbling motion, the drum should rotate at 65-85% of the critical speed (Wills B., 2006). In this study, 75% of the critical speed was selected. With an external drum diameter of $D_{\text{ext}} = 30$ cm and a wall thickness of $t = 2$ mm, the internal diameter becomes:

$$D_{\text{int}} = D_{\text{ext}} - 2t = 0.30 - 2 \cdot 0.002 = 0.296 \text{ m}$$

which gives the operating drum speed:

$$\omega = 0.75 \cdot N_c = 0.75 \cdot \frac{42.3}{\sqrt{0.296}} = 0.75 \cdot 77.75 = 58.3 \text{ rpm}$$

To reach this rotational speed, the gear ratio between the motor and the drum must be determined. Since the drum is driven by its supporting shafts, two successive reductions occur: - from the motor pulley to the shaft (belt and pulley transmission), - from the shaft to the drum (by friction).

Thus, the overall transmission ratio is:

$$R_{\text{total}} = R_{\text{motor-shaft}} \cdot R_{\text{shaft-drum}}$$

where

$$R_{\text{total}} = \frac{\omega_{\text{motor}}}{\omega_{\text{drum}}}, \quad R_{\text{shaft-drum}} = \frac{D_{\text{drum,ext}}}{D_{\text{shaft}}}$$

From the known geometry of the drum and shaft, and using the target drum speed and rotational speed of the chosen motor, the motor-shaft ratio can be obtained:

$$R_{\text{motor-shaft}} = \frac{R_{\text{total}}}{R_{\text{shaft-drum}}} = \frac{114.33}{12} = 9.53$$

Finally, the required shaft pulley diameter can be determined. Since the motor was supplied with a fixed pulley, only the shaft pulley $D_{\text{Pulley,shaft}}$ needs to be sized:

$$D_{\text{Pulley,shaft}} = D_{\text{Pulley,motor}} \cdot R_{\text{motor-shaft}}$$

which yields $D_{\text{Pulley,shaft}} = 210 \text{ mm}$. This dimension ensures the motor drives the drum at the correct rotational speed for proper tumbling.

All calculations were performed in a MATLAB environment, enabling automatic evaluation based on the drum geometry and motor characteristics. The complete MATLAB code is provided in Appendix B. As these results are theoretical, construction tolerances and material properties may require slight adjustments of the motor speed, highlighting the importance of the controller in achieving optimal operating conditions.

2.1.4 Prototype's Construction

The construction and testing of the prototype were carried out in Paris (France), on the upper deck of a riverboat. This location was mainly selected for logistical reasons, including noise considerations and convenient access to electricity.

The structural frame was assembled using a jigsaw and a drill, while all metal parts were cut to size with an angle grinder. Although welding would have provided additional strength and ease of assembly, it was not used due to the lack of equipment and skilled operators.

The drive system components were largely repurposed: the universal motor, motor pulley, and belt were salvaged from a broken washing machine. The shaft pulley was manufactured from wood, fitted tightly to the shaft, and further secured with a wooden clamp fixed to the wheel. A slight curvature was added to the outer surface of the pulley to allow the belt to self-center during operation.

Electrical connections were made with crimped terminals. The motor was controlled by a TRIAC-based speed controller, powered directly from the mains supply (220 V, 60 Hz).

The tumbling drums were fabricated from repurposed 13 L gas bottles as planned. They were first opened and filled with water to neutralize any remaining gas. Openings were then cut into the bottles with an angle grinder, and closing plates with reinforcing ridges were bonded using a two-part epoxy adhesive. The original circular openings were modified into square shapes, as these proved easier to cut with the grinding wheel.

Most of the machine’s components were sourced from a general hardware store (Leroy Merlin), while the stainless steel for the shafts and plates was purchased from a metal supplier, and the gas tanks used for the drums were obtained from a gas station. The total construction cost amounted to 831.00 € (783.72 CHF), with the detailed breakdown provided in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2. Cost breakdown of the prototype construction

Component	Cost [€]	Cost [CHF]
Structure	181.53	171.20
Metal plates and shafts	366.12	345.44
Bearings & rotating elements	123.28	116.28
Drums	130.09	122.87
Electronics	29.98	28.93
Total	831.00	783.72

Once the machine was assembled (see Figure 2.5), it was possible to proceed with testing both the machine and the tumbling process.

Figure 2.5. Fully built machine in operation with one drum

2.2 Testing of Waste Glass Tumbling

Testing the prototype tumbler machine was the most critical step of the thesis, as it determined whether the tumbling process could transform waste glass into a safe-to-handle material, and whether the machine itself was suitable for this purpose. This section first explains how the testing was organized (tests, cycles, parameters, and glass supply), and then details the methods used to register and evaluate the resulting data.

2.2.1 Tests, Cycles, and Parameters

The testing campaign was structured into several tests, each composed of multiple cycles. At the beginning of each test, the drums were filled with a fresh batch of waste glass, and the chosen parameters were set. The waste glass was sourced primarily from discarded bottles collected in Paris (from hotels or from public disposal). These bottles were manually broken into fragments of varying sizes by striking them with a metal bar inside a steel container.

A cycle was defined as a fixed duration of continuous machine operation. At the end of each cycle, a 1 kg sample of glass fragments was extracted from the drum and analyzed. The sample

was then returned to the drum so that the total glass quantity remained constant across cycles.

The selection of parameters and cycle lengths was refined progressively, as early results indicated the most promising directions for further testing. The two main parameters tested were the rotational speed of the drum and the size distribution of the initial waste glass.

Based on these parameters, three distinct tests were performed:

Test 1: 58 RPM, full size distribution of glass pieces

Test 2: 52 RPM, full size distribution of glass pieces

Test 3: 58 RPM, only the smallest category of glass pieces

These tests provided the data necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the tumbling process.

2.2.2 Sharpness Estimation

The primary characteristic to assess after tumbling was whether the glass fragments were still sharp. Since no standardized test or unit of measurement was available for this type of material, sharpness was evaluated through visual and tactile inspection.

A 10x magnifying glass was used to examine the edges of the fragments more closely. For each sample of 1 kg, observations were recorded in a logbook, and the sharpness was graded on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 corresponded to entirely dull edges, and 10 to extremely sharp fragments.

2.2.3 Size Distribution

Another important aspect was the evolution of the size distribution between cycles, as this indicated whether the tumbling process was effective at breaking larger glass pieces into smaller ones.

For each 1 kg sample, the distribution was measured using a set of sieves and a precision scale. Two sieves were used, dividing the fragments into three size categories:

- larger than 30 mm,
- between 30 mm and 10 mm,
- smaller than 10 mm.

The 30 mm sieve was a square-holed steel wire sieve, and the 10 mm sieve was a perforated metal plate with circular holes. Each fraction was weighed with a scale precise to 1 g, and the results were converted into percentages to simplify data analysis.

2.2.4 Machine Operation

Finally, the operational behavior of the machine was monitored throughout the testing. A log was kept for each cycle to record observations of the machine's performance and any issues encountered. This information helped validate the current prototype and identify possible improvements for future designs using the same architecture.

In addition, power consumption was measured for several cycles by connecting a wattmeter between the TRIAC controller and the mains electricity supply. This allowed an estimation of the machine's energy demand under operating conditions.

3 RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the experiments conducted with the tumbling machine. The analysis focuses on three main aspects: (i) the evolution of glass sharpness during tumbling, (ii) the changes in size distribution of the glass pieces, and (iii) the machine's performance in terms of power consumption, operation, and possible improvements.

3.1 Sharpness estimation

Based on the hardness of glass and experiences from similar processes for rock tumbling, it was initially hypothesized that around 10 hours of tumbling would be necessary to sufficiently dull glass pieces. To test this assumption, the first experiment was carried out with a cycle length of one hour.

The results, however, showed that most dulling occurred within the first hour, as seen in Figure 3.1. The sharpness decreased rapidly at the start and then slowed down, indicating diminishing returns with longer cycles. The overall curve was obtained by calculating the weighted average of the sharpness score according to the percentage weight of each size category.

Figure 3.1. Evolution of the sharpness score for Test 1

To better capture the early evolution, the second test used 15-minute cycles. The results (Figure 3.2) confirmed the trend observed in the first test: sharpness decreases rapidly within the first hour, reaching values around 2/10, after which additional cycles have only limited effect.

Figure 3.2. Evolution of the sharpness score for Test 2

The difference in sharpness can be easily observed visually with only one hour of tumbling, as shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3. Two glass waste pieces, before tumbling (left) and after 1 hour of tumbling (right)

When sharpness is analyzed by size category (Figures 3.4 and 3.5), two additional phenomena appear:

- **Dependence on size:** Larger pieces dull faster and to a greater extent than smaller ones, although all categories eventually show a slowdown in dulling past 45 minutes.
- **Increase in sharpness due to conchoidal fractures:** For pieces larger than 10 mm, new fractures occasionally appeared after prolonged tumbling, creating fresh sharp edges. These fractures, called conchoidal fractures (resembling those found in primitive flint tools) caused the sharpness score of larger pieces to increase again, and the apparition of small glass pieces (<5 mm) with only sharp edges. An example is shown in Figure 3.6; note the new sharp edge that appeared in the middle of the dull edge.

Figure 3.4. Sharpness evolution per category, Test 1

Figure 3.5. Sharpness evolution per category, Test 2

Figure 3.6. Conchoidal fracture on a glass piece

These phenomena can be explained by kinetic energy: larger pieces carry more energy at the same rotation speed, accelerating dulling but occasionally generating conchoidal fractures. To reduce this issue, Test 2 was also conducted at a lower speed of 52 RPM instead of 58 RPM.

The results confirmed that this reduced the occurrence of conchoidal fractures, achieving a balance between efficient dulling and limited creation of new sharp edges on later cycles (see Figure 3.5).

The results of the first two tests indicated that the smallest fraction of glass pieces (below 10 mm) was significantly less affected by the tumbling process and did not become as dull as the larger fragments. Consequently, the third test was dedicated exclusively to this fraction, with the objective of determining whether it was possible to dull these small pieces and, if so, how much tumbling time would be required. For this purpose, the drum was filled solely with glass fragments smaller than 10 mm, which were selected using the same 10 mm sieve employed during the sample analysis. The evolution of the sharpness score for this test is presented in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7. Sharpness score evolution for glass pieces below 10 mm

The results show that dulling this size category is indeed possible, but it requires substantially more time than for larger fragments. To illustrate, achieving a sharpness score of 2.5/10 required less than 45 minutes for pieces larger than 30 mm, and under 60 minutes for pieces between 10 and 30 mm (see Figure 3.5). In contrast, the <10 mm fraction required 270 minutes (4.5 hours) to reach the same sharpness level. Furthermore, the sharpness curve for this test displayed a slower, more gradual decline, without the steep drop observed when processing the full size distribution.

In summary, the series of tests demonstrated that the tumbling process is an effective method for dulling waste glass, typically requiring about one hour for a mixed batch. The findings also confirmed that the effectiveness of the process strongly depends on particle size: larger fragments (>10 mm) dull considerably faster than smaller ones (<10 mm). In addition, rotational speed was shown to be a key parameter influencing the outcome: operating at 52 RPM (67% of the critical speed) provided better dulling with only a minimal increase in process duration compared to 58 RPM (75% of the critical speed).

3.2 Size distribution

Before conducting the tests, it was hypothesized that the tumbling process would break down the larger glass pieces into smaller fragments, resulting in a more homogeneous size distribution with few or no large pieces remaining. During each sampling, the size distribution of the glass was measured, producing the following results for Tests 1 and 2 (Test 3 contained only one size category):

Figure 3.8. Size distribution of glass pieces during Test 1

Figure 3.9. Size distribution of glass pieces during Test 2

From these graphs, it is visible that no clear trend emerges in the evolution of the size distribution, and distribution stays the same over the cycles. Larger pieces are not consistently broken down into smaller ones—at least not to a measurable extent. Sharpness testing suggested that the largest fragments could undergo conchoidal fractures, producing small shards. However, these events did not lead to noticeable changes in overall size distribution, mainly because the new fragments were small and occurred only rarely.

3.3 Machine power consumption and operation

Power consumption: While the machine was in operation, the power drawn from the entire machine was tested with the help of a wattmeter. Two configurations were tested: one with a single drum and another with both drums loaded (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10. Power consumption of the machine during the first 120 seconds for one and two drums

In both cases, the machine displayed a power spike of about 190 W, stabilizing after roughly 40 seconds. For the single drum setup, average consumption was around 143 W, while the two-drum configuration required approximately 187 W.

Machine operation: Over the course of many hours of testing, the machine generally performed well, requiring only minor upgrades and repairs:

- *Sound proofing:* Initially, the drums rotated directly on the metal shaft. Because the reclaimed gas bottles' profile were not perfectly circular, they bounced while turning, producing continuous noise measured above 90 dB (measured from one meter). To mitigate this, foam pipe insulation sleeves were placed around the shaft, creating a softer contact surface that absorbed vibrations and reduced the noise to about 65 dB (measured from one meter). Given the added radius of the sleeves, this changed the reduction ratio for the shaft-drum stage, but this difference was small enough to be easily managed by the TRIAC controller.

However, foam proved unsuitable for long-term use, wearing out quickly and requiring replacement. A more durable material, such as recycled tire rubber, would be better suited for this role.

- *Vibrations:* Although the foam sleeves reduced vibrations significantly, the machine's wooden frame still experienced enough movement to cause wood screws to loosen over time. All fasteners, including machine screws, had to be regularly checked. As wood screws have limited torque resistance loses grip after being driven repeatedly into the same hole, the wooden structure had to be reinforced with additional metal plates.

For permanent installations, a fully metallic structure would be preferable, either welded or bolted together, with the use of thread locker and nyloc nuts to ensure resistance against loosening. Furthermore, mounting the bearings on rubber blocks could further reduce vibration transmission to the frame.

- *Price:* While cost reduction was not the primary focus, the use of reclaimed and reused components reflected the constraints of settings like Cape Maclear. A lower construction cost would also make the machine more accessible for small communities with limited funds. The stainless-steel shafts and plates, chosen for their mechanical resistance and weatherproofing properties, were disproportionately expensive, representing 366€ (44% of the total machine cost).

Since outdoor storage requires some corrosion resistance, stainless steel seemed appealing, but carbon steel would have been sufficient. Light oxidation on shafts and drums would not impair operation and would drastically reduce expenses. In Paris, ordering the same parts in S235 carbon steel would cost only 80.75€, representing a 78% saving compared to the 304L stainless steel used (leMetal.fr, n.d.).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated that tumbling is a practical and efficient method to process glass waste into a safer material for handling and disposal. Experimental results confirmed that, under the right machine settings, a batch of waste glass can be rendered safe in approximately one hour. The tests showed that excessive speed can cause new fractures and sharp edges to form, undermining the process, and that dulling is size-dependent: larger pieces dull faster and to a greater extent than smaller ones. At the same time, tumbling alone proved insufficient to break down large pieces into smaller fragments, indicating that complementary size reduction techniques would be necessary if modifying the size distribution is also a goal.

Beyond the experimental findings, the project contributed to the design and validation of a machine architecture tailored for this process. The use of two parallel shafts and removable drums proved to be a reliable and robust configuration, with the added advantage of scalability should higher tumbling capacity be required. The design also confirmed the feasibility of incorporating reused and recycled components, from structural parts such as the drums to electrical components like the motor. This not only reduces costs but also demonstrates the design's flexibility to adapt to available parts in an urban environment. In addition, the adaptable power system further enhances the machine's practicality: it can operate both on mains electricity with a TRIAC controller or on direct current with DC–DC converters, opening the possibility of solar-powered operation in regions where access to reliable electricity may be limited.

The integration of tumbling into municipal waste processing chains could represent a significant improvement in safety, particularly in vulnerable communities such as Cape Maclear, where unmanaged glass waste often leads to injuries. The next step for the project should focus on strategies to incorporate this additional processing stage into local waste management practices. This will require not only technical adaptation but also strong community engagement to ensure acceptance and adoption.

Looking further ahead, the valorization of tumbled glass presents an important area for exploration. Once rendered safe, the material could be repurposed for applications in construction, landscaping, or even artistic projects, thereby transforming a hazardous waste into a valuable resource. Such pathways could provide social, environmental, and economic benefits simultaneously: reducing the burden of injuries, lowering municipal waste management costs,

and creating opportunities for local economic activity. By demonstrating the technical feasibility of the tumbling process, this project also provides answers on a low-tech, sustainable, and low-cost approach to managing glass waste, which can be integrated into broader glass waste management strategies and explored within the possibilities of a circular economy.

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APPENDIX A - MATLAB CALCULATIONS AND RESULTS FOR SHAFT DIAMETER

The following MATLAB script was used to compute the minimum shaft diameters for both solid circular and annular profiles, considering several material options.

Listing A.1. MATLAB script for shaft diameter calculations

```
% Constants
g = 9.81;
sig_304L = 170*10^6; % elastic limit Pa
sig_6060 = 80*10^6;
sig_316L = 200*10^6;
sig_s235 = 235*10^6;

% Variables
m_drum = 11; % Kg
m_glass = 25.7;
m = m_drum + m_glass;

L_drum = 0.45; % drum's length
L = L_drum + 0.075*2; % shaft's length between 2 bearings

SF = 3; % Safety Factor

% Force & moment calculations
F = m * g * SF; % total punctual force at shaft center
M = F * L / 4; % max bending moment

% Circular profile
d_circ_304L = ((32*M)/(pi*sig_304L))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
```

```

d_circ_316L = ((32*M)/(pi*sig_316L))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
d_circ_s235 = ((32*M)/(pi*sig_s235))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
d_circ_6060 = ((32*M)/(pi*sig_6060))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm

```

```

% Annular profile

```

```

Ratio_D_304L = (32*M)/(pi*sig_304L);
Ratio_D_316L = (32*M)/(pi*sig_316L);
Ratio_D_s235 = (32*M)/(pi*sig_s235);
Ratio_D_6060 = (32*M)/(pi*sig_6060);

```

```

% If defined pipe thickness = x% of pipe diameter

```

```

x = 10; % percentage
x = x / 100;

```

```

d_ann_304L = ((32*M)/((1-(1-x)^4)*pi*sig_304L))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
d_ann_316L = ((32*M)/((1-(1-x)^4)*pi*sig_316L))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
d_ann_s235 = ((32*M)/((1-(1-x)^4)*pi*sig_s235))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm
d_ann_6060 = ((32*M)/((1-(1-x)^4)*pi*sig_6060))^(1/3) * 10^3; % mm

```

```

% If thickness is uncorrelated with pipe diameter

```

```

thick = 2*10^-3; % thickness in m

```

```

syms D

```

```

eqn_304L = (D^4-(D-thick)^4)/D == (32*M)/(pi*sig_304L);
eqn_316L = (D^4-(D-thick)^4)/D == (32*M)/(pi*sig_316L);
eqn_s235 = (D^4-(D-thick)^4)/D == (32*M)/(pi*sig_s235);
eqn_6060 = (D^4-(D-thick)^4)/D == (32*M)/(pi*sig_6060);

```

```

S_304L = solve(eqn_304L, D);
var = vpa(S_304L);
d_ann_thick_304L = double(var(3)) * 10^3;

```

```

S_316L = solve(eqn_316L, D);
var = vpa(S_316L);
d_ann_thick_316L = double(var(3)) * 10^3;

```

```

S_s235 = solve(eqn_s235, D);

```

```
var = vpa(S_s235);
d_ann_thick_s235 = double(var(3)) * 10^3;
```

```
S_6060 = solve(eqn_6060, D);
var = vpa(S_6060);
d_ann_thick_6060 = double(var(3)) * 10^3;
```

The last part of the Matlab files calculated diameter required for axles with annular profiles, and yield the following results :

Table A.1. Minimum shaft diameter for different materials for annular profile and a thickness of 10% the total diameter

Material	d_{ann} [mm]
304L Stainless Steel	30.45
316L Stainless Steel	28.84
6060 Aluminium Alloy	39.14
S235 Structural Steel	27.33

Table A.2. Minimum shaft diameter for different materials for annular profile and a thickness of 2 mm

Material	d_{ann} [mm]
304L Stainless Steel	36.31
316L Stainless Steel	33.59
6060 Aluminium Alloy	52.26
S235 Structural Steel	31.10

APPENDIX B - MATLAB CALCULATIONS AND RESULTS FOR TRANSMISSION RATIOS

```
% Rotation speed
% Aimed rotation speed for the Drum :
D_ext = 300; % Exterior drum diameter, in mm
thickness = 2; % Material, in mm
D_int = D_ext - 2*thickness; % Interior drum diameter

Crit_speed = 42.3/sqrt(D_int*10^-3); %Critical speed, in rpm
Rot_speed = Crit_speed*0.75 % Pratictal rotation speed = 0.6-0.8*critical sp

% Machine mechanical parameters
Motor_speed = 10000*2/3; %rpm Estmation of around 12 000 rpm max for the mot
D_shaft = 25; %in mm

% Transmission : Double reduction gear :
% Motor pulley -> Shaft pulley -> Shaft -> Drum
Ratio_needed = Motor_speed/Rot_speed % Ratio_needed:1

% Gear Ratio shaft/drum
Ratio_shaft_drum = D_ext/D_shaft

% Gear Ratio motor/shaft
Ratio_motor_shaft = Ratio_needed/Ratio_shaft_drum

% Motor - shaft transmission
Pulley_motor = 22; %in mm or nb of teeth
Pulley_shaft = Pulley_motor*Ratio_motor_shaft %Pulley_shaft > D_shaft
```